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Deliverable Administration and Summary

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Work Programme Description	The course materials will be assembled in conjunction with the learning activities developed within the network. A short targeted module on a housing studies topic will be developed, to be delivered over a period of approximately 6 weeks, using live and asynchronous learning activities and interactions.				
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Table of Contents

1 Executive Summary	3
2 Introduction	4
2.1 Purpose and target group.....	4
2.2 Contribution of partners	4
2.3 Relations to other activities in the project.....	5
3 MOOC Design	6
3.1 Constructively aligned learning	6
3.1.1 Constructive alignment and Bloom’s taxonomy.....	6
3.1.2 Knowledge construction in architecture education	7
3.1.3 Bloom’s taxonomy and the Housing Design MOOC.....	7
4 Design of Learning.....	8
4.1 MOOC evolution, meetings and timetabling	11
5 MOOC Delivery	13
5.1 First edition: 1 September - November 2015	13
5.1.1 Pattern of learner engagement.....	14
5.1.2 Discussion forums and feedback.....	14
5.1.3 Modifications for the second edition.....	15
5.2 Second edition: 2 May - June 2016.....	15
5.2.1 Pattern of learner engagement.....	16
6 Discussion	17
6.1 Original Evaluation plan	17
6.2 Numbers registering	17
6.3 Numbers completing	18
6.4 Technical knowledge and ability requirements.....	18
7 Conclusions.....	19
8 References.....	21
9 APPENDIX A. Design Template	22
10 APPENDIX B. Topic Descriptions.....	25
10.1 Module 1: Participatory Processes	25
10.2 Module 2: Energy Efficiency	28
10.3 Module 3: Sustainable Materials.....	30
10.4 Module 4: Parametric Design.....	32
10.5 Module 5: Digital Fabrication	35
10.6 Tutors biographies.....	37
10.7 Section 3: Links to OIKONET Project Goals	38
11 Glossary.....	39

1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document summarises the purpose, underlying thinking and development activities for the Massive Open Online Course (MOOC) developed within the WP4 Pedagogical Activities of the OIKONET project. Two iterations of the MOOC were designed, planned and delivered during the course of the project.

The MOOC subject is “Housing Design: from Concept to Fabrication” and it was intended as an introduction to the design of housing for novice learners. The pedagogical design is based on constructive alignment as implemented in previous OIKODOMOS projects¹, and the topics follow the same pattern and broad scope as implemented in the OIKONET workshop held in Lisbon in July 2014 (see Deliverable 4.3 “International Workshops (Lisbon)”). The programme of the workshop integrated five subjects around the design of a housing prototype: sustainability, energy efficiency, parametric design, digital fabrication, and participatory processes. For the MOOC, the housing prototype has been simplified to suit the starting knowledge of the students and the concept of a “Dolls House” (“Play House” second edition of the MOOC) was adopted as a unifying theme. The five main topics, treated as individual course modules, led participants from social considerations for design of this simple model through a series of modules leading up to the final outputs required for digital fabrication.

The MOOC relied on self-study and peer learning, with the learning activities designed to encourage and support both. Formative assessment tasks were used within the modules, building up knowledge and skills which could be brought together into submitting an entry to a competition for the best design.

The Canvas MOOC environment was used for delivery. Five tutors from project partners collaboratively designed and subsequently completed a common design template (Appendix A) which was used to structure the modules and select the resources and assessments (see module descriptions in Appendix B). Tutors worked with the lead author of this report as coordinator. Each tutor facilitated the delivery of their module.

Two iterations of the MOOC were delivered -from September thru November 2015, and from May thru June 2016- with modifications to some of the course materials and delivery processes being implemented for the second iteration. The differences between cohorts for the two iterations complicated the analysis of the results and limited the conclusions which could be drawn. This was further complicated by the small number of learners who completed the requirements for the modules or for the course overall.

The course was designed on sound pedagogical principles for working within a MOOC environment. Overall the authors/tutors felt that the course was well designed but that it failed to engage students as members of a community of learners. The reasons for this are discussed and will be addressed in future iterations of the MOOC.

¹ See [OIKODOMOS Compendium](#)

2 INTRODUCTION

2.1 Purpose and target group

The nature of a MOOC (Massive Open Online Course) is to open up a subject to a diverse and geographically dispersed group of learners. The OIKONET MOOC was designed to make available an introduction to the design of housing to novice learners. Guidance from Canvas network, the MOOC platform provider, indicated that this subject could be of wide appeal and therefore likely to attract between five hundred and thousands of learners, from a wide range of backgrounds and abilities.

2.2 Contribution of partners

The list of partners and the modules which they contributed to the MOOC are given below:

Partner No	Partner	Module number and Name
P15	University of Cyprus (UCY)	1. Participatory processes
P25	Lisbon University Institute (ISCTE)	2. Energy efficiency
P3	Faculty of Architecture, Slovak University of Technology (FASTU)	3. Sustainable materials
P15	University of Cyprus (UCY)	4. Parametric design
P25	Lisbon University Institute (ISCTE)	5. Digital fabrication

In addition, the external advisor (Paul Riddy) provided the pedagogic design, and coordinated the MOOC development and delivery.

Each partner completed the design template for their MOOC as provided in Appendix A. These provide a summary of the learning role of their module including the aims, learning outcomes, content and learning and teaching method's which were to be employed during the MOOC. There were some small modifications as the writing of the materials developed and the module leaders begin to experiment with the Canvas MOOC (Canvas, 2014) environment.

2.3 Relations to other activities in the project

The initial idea for development of the MOOC was linked to the learning space “Introduction to Housing” (see Deliverable 4.1 “Learning Spaces”), which it was felt could be turned into a subject suitable for novice students. Following the Lisbon Workshop in July 2014 (see Deliverable 4.3 “Lisbon Workshop”), the main subject was revised to reflect a similar scope of activities to those encompassed within the workshop. Several of the main tutors participating in Lisbon were tutors for the MOOC, and brought some of the resources and learning activities used.

The development of the MOOC led OIKONET partners to reflect upon the approach to design and integrate learning processes which cover a range of complex topics, for a relatively novice audience. The coherence of the MOOC was based on the sequential development of these topics as individual modules, starting with the design considerations for a house and working through to fabrication. This forced a review of the learning and teaching methods and led to the team selecting tools and resources which could be available for use in other applications, including within workspaces and within partner institutions own programs.

The MOOC was made freely available, and reached learners who were widely distributed geographically. The connection with the OIKONET project was foregrounded in the MOOC description leading to the MOOC having a joint educational and dissemination role.

Some of the partners in the MOOC team made the resources available as additional material for in-house courses. This also served a dissemination role within their institutions.

The MOOC also provided a showcase for partner’s expertise and was a demonstration of a significant and productive collaboration between a small group of OIKONET partners, the output of which was globally accessible, including to staff and students of a partner institutions.

3 MOOC DESIGN

The design of the MOOC followed the same underlying pedagogical model as elaborated for the OIKODOMOS project. The main features are outlined below. This borrows heavily from the methodology developed in the previous OIKODOMOS project (Riddy, Depuydt, & Madrazo, 2014).

3.1 Constructively aligned learning

The underlying learning and teaching philosophy is constructivist which matches well with the underpinning model of learning within housing studies, theoretical concepts mainly being explored and understood by placing them in a practical context. The massive nature of a MOOC reflects the very large numbers of students who frequently participate, making it impossible for tutors to interact with students on an individual basis. This adds a new dimension to the educational experiences of previous OIKODOMOS projects, necessitating design which allows much greater potential for online interaction and peer learning, mediated by the online environment. The MOOC environment was designed to facilitate the social construction of knowledge (Vygotsky, 1978) in which the interactions between learners are deliberately fostered to support the learning process.

3.1.1 Constructive alignment and Bloom's taxonomy

The underlying model for the design of learning is Constructive Alignment (Biggs & Tang, 2011), illustrated in the diagram below.

Figure 1. Schematic of the aligned learning and teaching model based on Biggs work (Biggs & Tang, 2011)

As indicated in Figure 1, this methodology seeks alignment of the various elements with a key consideration being everything that is to be assessed is underpinned by a supporting learning process. In an ideal situation the first design iteration would start with aims and learning outcomes followed by alignment of the other elements around the ellipse. In practice, a designer of learning might start at other points and align by cross-checking and subsequent iteration around the cycle. In this aligned model the assessment methods should be selected to align with the learning outcomes, assignments being set to test the students understanding as indicated by the *active verbs* used within the learning outcomes.

Bloom's Taxonomy of Educational Objectives (Bloom, 1956) was used to guide selection of the active verbs used for writing the learning outcomes, thereby helping to provide overall consistency in the way the learning outcomes were written and their final form. The schematic below provides the hierarchy for the writing of verbs when applying Bloom's taxonomy.

Figure 2. Schematic of Bloom's cognitive domain

For each level Bloom provided examples of active verbs which could be used to describe the competence or skill to be developed and subsequently assessed or measured. Applying the taxonomy to the development of students' abilities, we would expect them to become more adept at activities which require the higher level skills, such as associated with the Synthesis and Evaluation levels, as they progress through a programme of learning,

3.1.2 Knowledge construction in architecture education

In conventional architecture courses the information which students engage embodies conceptual structure. Van House has suggested: "Information artefacts, including texts and images, are not simply reflections or carriers of knowledge. They shape and reflect practice and are instrumental in creating and re-creating knowledge as well as coordinating work across space and time" (Van House, 2003). A difficulty in designing the MOOC was that the students could not be expected to bring the depth of experience gained from working with the wide range of integrated and overlapping topics which the discipline demands. Therefore, the MOOC was designed to lead students along a more linear development pathway than those courses which are longer or with substantial pre-requisites.

3.1.3 Bloom's taxonomy and the Housing Design MOOC

This MOOC was intended as an introduction to the topic of housing design. As there were no pre-requisites for studying the MOOC, the basic design of learning and selection of resources was largely constrained to working within the lower levels of the taxonomy, Knowledge to Application (see Figure 2). However, modules 4 and 5 led learners to design a simple Doll's or Play House (in the second edition), in part synthesising the knowledge which they had learnt in earlier modules. For those that attempted modules 4 and 5, this would push their learning into more sophisticated engagement with the materials and use of higher-level cognitive skills.

4 DESIGN OF LEARNING

The scope of the MOOC was based on the program carried out in the Lisbon workshop and covers the same five topics included in the workshop program: sustainability, energy efficiency, parametric design, digital fabrication, and participatory processes (see Appendix B for details of the contents covered by these topics).

The initial plan was to design and deliver a single MOOC. After completion of the first MOOC, MOOC 1, the team were curious about how the student's engagement and learning might be enhanced. With the bulk of the resources already developed and organised, the tutors decided to make the relatively small changes outlined in 5.1.3 and to deliver MOOC 2.

MOOC objectives:

To devise and implement a custom design process for housing integrating user's specific needs with environmental constraints through the use of advanced design and fabrication tools. Five complementary topics, organised as individual modules, were addressed: participation, energy efficiency, sustainable materials, parametric design and digital fabrication.

The module leaders applied the model of constructive alignment to identify the following design elements:

- Overview
- Aims
- Learning Outcomes
- Learning Tasks (Activities)
- Learning Resources
- Formative assessment

MOOC design process:

As the MOOC design evolved, a Dolls House was chosen as a simple conceptual theme used to unify the topics. Although the topics were developed sequentially through the MOOC, each linked to the theme and to the other topics as appropriate. The parametric design model of the Dolls House was introduced conceptually in week one and each of the modules discussed and led learners to be able to select information appropriate for their parametric designs. As the course developed the learners assembled a set of information which they could use in their final module and to support their entry to the competition.

In the first edition of the MOOC, one week was dedicated to each module plus a wrap up week. The final week included a competition for the best Dolls House design, from which a winner could be selected and a model of their design produced.

Each week opened with a semi-live session which followed a standard format:

- Live video welcome to the week, general questions
- Starting topic for a small group discussion (15 -20 minutes) / feedback from groups – e.g. via Twitter or in a more discursive environment

- Comments from the facilitator(s)
- Presentation / Round table discussion between experts, 20 minutes
 - Respond to questions
- Readings (including videos, etc.) and tasks for the week.
- Close

Week 1 also opened the MOOC, provided an introduction to the facilitators' and a map of the MOOC contents with the learners' journey, based on the diagram in Figure 3 below.

Participants were expected to complete tasks during the week and post relevant outputs back to a discussion board. Participants were grouped and where appropriate asked to provide feedback on each other's work within their groups. For most tasks, simple assessment criteria were provided as a guide for participants to comment on each other's work.

Tutors sampled the work submitted each week and responded to questions and comments from learners via topic based discussion boards and the Course discussion board.

OIKONET MOOC DEVELOPMENT/ FRAMEWORK DESIGN PROCESS - HOUSING DESIGN: FROM CONCEPT TO FABRICATION

DESIGN PROCESS

Figure 3. Sequence of MOOC topics (figure by Alexandra Paio)

4.1 MOOC evolution, meetings and timetabling

The MOOC concept was first presented at the Pedagogical Activities (Work package 4) meeting in Barcelona, in January 2014. This provided an overview of a typical MOOC platform and the learning and teaching activities and methods it would support. Following the presentation, a number of partners expressed an interest in being involved in the development of the OIKONET MOOC. This gradually evolved into a team, in conjunction with the development of other work package activities and shifting demands on individual's time.

In parallel, a **selection of a MOOC environment** began. Following discussions with a number of existing MOOC users and reviewing web-based information on some of the options the Canvas environment was selected. The features which led to it being selected were:

- Open to reputable groups and organisations;
- Platform well established;
- Ease of use;
- Tools available within its environment;
- Simplicity in linking to non-core tools, development support available to tutors;
- Free but business options available (for if OIKONET partners wanted to subsequently develop their own courses);
- Flexibility in agreement of contract terms.

The MOOC was delivered twice during the course of the project, with the approach to delivery modified between the two iterations. The sequence of meetings and development stages is listed in the table below:

Table 1. Meetings and Activities Timetable

Stage Dates	Activity
pre-March 2015	Design Information Template designed, tutors began to complete the template
MOOC 1	
March - April	Development of MOOC materials
Friday 17 th April	Skype Update meeting
Friday 8 th May	Skype meeting / Team start review MOOC materials
Monday 18 th May	All feedback to Paul / partners
Friday 22 nd May	Skype meeting
Friday 29 th May	Skype Course review 1 with Katie (from Canvas)
June	Finalise materials / test environment
Friday 19 th June	Skype Update meeting
Friday 3 rd July (Cottbus? / Skype)	Final course description to Katie
Monday 27th July	All materials finalised – MOOC released to Canvas to publicise
Monday August 10 th 2015	Open for enrolment (earlier if we are ready)
Monday August 24 th	Skype Update meeting
Monday Sept 7th 2015	Go live (Wrap-Up week 12 th Oct, end date Friday 16 th Oct)
Weeks beginning Sept 7 th , 14 th , May, 21 st , 28 th , 5 th Oct,	MOOC topics 1-5

Monday 12 th Oct	MOOC Wrap-Up /Summary week
Friday 23 rd Oct	Skype Wash-up meeting
MOOC 2	
22/01/2016	Review and planning meeting, within Brussels WP4 meeting
February & March	Editing and re-organisation of materials
03/02/2016	Skype Update meeting with tutors
08/02/2016	Skype Discussion about Integration of revised modules with Vasco
15/02/2016	Skype Module Development Progress meeting with tutors
21/02/2016	Skype Module Development Progress meeting with tutors
31/03/2016	Skype Update meeting with Vasco
03/04/2016	Skype Update meeting with Elina
21/04/2016	Skype Update meeting with Vasco & Elina
13/05/2016	Skype Final Launch preparation meeting with tutors
May 16 2016	Go live, week 1 preparation
Weeks beginning May, 23 rd , 30 th , June 6 th , 13 th , 20 th	MOOC topics 1-5
Week beginning June 27 th	Competition submissions, judging and sign off
September 22 nd 2016	Wash-up meeting, within the OIKONET conference

Skype meeting dates are highlighted in blue text

5 MOOC DELIVERY

The two editions of the MOOC are briefly described below, describing the sequence of activities and the students' engagement. Based on the experiences of the first edition, the changes implemented for the second edition are explained.

5.1 First edition: 1 September - November 2015

The MOOC opening session, introduced the tutors, the modules and the progression of the MOOC. Each module was delivered over a period of one week, with a further week available for completion of assignments and submission of entries to the competition. Each of the modules followed the same pattern of delivery:

- Opening live and streamed presentation (Google Hangouts and YouTube)
- Participants automatically grouped to participate in a live activity based on materials and questions
- Re-convene with tutor after 20-30 minutes discussion
- Task setting for the week
- Mid-week live video stream for tutors to respond to live questions and/or comment or to respond to questions from the peer-discussions
- End of week live feedback on tasks/ response to questions / wrap-up presentation
- Tutor check-back/ handover during the live-session for the following week

As indicated in the module descriptions, activities were designed to use peer interaction as a significant element of the learning process, participants using resources, carrying out activities and giving feedback to each other within groups to which they were assigned automatically. Support forums for each module/topic were provided with tutors providing a live video stream to respond to queries mid-way through the week. Students were expected to spend approximately 4 hours/week working on the MOOC assignments and discussing their work with other students.

The first three modules led students to discover the essential elements of housing design. The last two modules were more complex in that learners would need sufficient computational skills to allow them to download, install and learn how to use some fairly complex software, at a beginner's level. (The software downloads were large.) The latter modules were supported by online tutorials developed by the software companies and by tutorials specially developed by the tutors. It was anticipated that these modules would extend the interest of the course to individuals who had some background knowledge of the discipline, such as students of architecture and engineering.

The course was originally planned to run for 6 weeks, but this was extended in response to the independent requests of a number of active participants, because they were having trouble meeting the assignment submission deadlines. Module materials were released on the Sunday evening for the week following, but left available for the duration of the MOOC.

Registration was opened 2 weeks before the course began and overall numbers for the MOOC are given below:

Course opened	Course completed	No of completers	Number of non-participants
253 (7 th Sept 2015)	560 (November 5 th 2015)	1	~300

5.1.1 Pattern of learner engagement

Only a few of the students participated, so the planned discussion activities could not take place. This signalled a lack of engagement with live sessions which continued throughout the course. Each of the live sessions were recorded and linked to from the relevant module page. The opening video has been watched over 200 times and although we have not been able to access the viewers' details this is reasonable given the initial number of active participants. It's reasonable to assume that students who completed a module's assignments had also watched the videos but we were not able to access the viewers' details.

From the start, around 50% of participants didn't view any of the pages. The majority of participants accessed the resources through the "Home" / start page and in general followed the modules in the design sequence. Progressing from modules 1-4 there was a rapid drop down to around 80 participants during module 1/ week 1 followed by a reduction in the page viewings for each of the following modules, apart from a small increase for module 5 (Digital Fabrication). There were a significant number who entered the MOOC via the Digital Fabrication module, although the majority of these didn't follow the module.

The number of participants completing assignments was considerably less than active participants, with 18 completing the assignments for the first module, a similar number for modules 2 & 3, with further reduction for module 4. Only two people completed assignments for the final module. One individual submitted an entry for the competition but the information set was incomplete.

Viewing of some of the resources was initiated from over 1500 separate IP (Internet protocol) addresses. Learners from 53 countries and from all continents registered, but these represented less than 0.5% of learners, the remainder being from the USA. Although the course materials were written to be generic, this might mean that there was a mismatch in the design of material with the predominate group of learners' expectations, arising from the difference of experience within their own educational culture.

With the requirement for downloading of large files, there is likely to be a correlation between network access/ geographical location and the drop-off in participation, but as the majority of learners who were registered were from the USA we would need more detailed data to be able to assess this.

Compared with the enrolment figures and the number of separate IP addresses used, the small number of students who actively participated, as compared to those who only read the materials, meant that the grouping activities and discussion forums could not function effectively. Very few of the learners (around 20 of 530 registered) were *active in being prepared* to exchange work and critique the work of others. This severely compromised the intended peer-learning activities of the course. The requirement for participation in discussions was therefore dropped, and students allowed to submit their assignments for review by the module tutor. As a result, the learning process became more activity driven, supported by online resources and tutors. Although this is theoretically an appropriate teaching approach for working in a MOOC environment (Stacey, 2013), the drop-out and low completion rates merit further examination of the approach.

5.1.2 Discussion forums and feedback

The discussion forums for each of the modules were little used, questions being mainly process or topic focussed. Emails from around ~50% of active learners valued the materials and modules, but no participants completed the in-course online feedback questionnaire. In our experience, returns on electronically delivered questionnaires are small, usually in the range 10-50%. The return rate in itself is therefore not surprising, but it does reinforce the overall lack of student's motivation to engage and perhaps their lack of connection with the tutors and other students.

5.1.3 Modifications for the second edition

Following on from the above discussion, the key challenges encountered during the first edition of the MOOC and the changes implemented were:

Table 2: Changes for the second edition (MOOC 2)

Challenge	Response incorporated into second edition
Learners slow to engage at start of course	Start-up week introduced before first module begins. Information on software downloads highlighted.
Insufficient participation for automated grouping for peer-learning activities	Individual assignment submission with selection commented on by tutor. Discussion boards available for individuals to establish peer discussions about their work
Very-low participation in live video sessions	No live-video sessions. Recorded videos made linked to module pages. Tutors respond to selection questions raised in module or general discussion boards
Learners unable to complete assignments in the weekly time scale	All assignments for modules 1-3 given common submission deadline at the end of week 4. Requirement for Digital Fabrication of a parametric design removed for completion of the course.
Poor take-up of Parametric Design and Digital Fabrication modules.	Previous point, + final output changed to a Play House design, which could be from a parametric or drawn model. Digital Fabrication became an optional module, not required for completion of the course.
Few competition entries	The final output was changed from a <i>Doll's House</i> to a <i>Play House</i> , to provide more scope for research into and development of the design. Digital Fabrication of the final design was made optional.

5.2 Second edition: 2 May - June 2016

See the table above for the changes which were introduced. The same core resources were used but the module guidance re-written to accommodate and incorporate the changes. The most significant change through all modules was the removal of peer-discussion as a required element for the assignments. Competition entries were based on the design of a *Play House* which did not need to be machine printed. The use of a *Play House* as the final artefact to be designed, instead of the *Dolls' House* used in MOOC 1, provided a clearer and more natural coherence through the modules to the development of this final course artefact.

Course opened	Course completed	No of completers	Number of non-participants
95 (16th May 2016)	232 (26 th June 2016)	0	176

5.2.1 Pattern of learner engagement

(The usage statistics information which Canvas provided changed between the two iterations of the MOOC. In short, this meant that same list of detailed interaction data was not available.)

From the start of the MOOC less than 25% of registered participants viewed any of the pages. Review of the “Access Report” for learners completing assignments and around 10% of active learners who didn’t complete any assignments, indicates that they general went through the materials systematically, starting from the course intro pages and working through the modules in sequence, although there were also a few learners who were less systematic. The working pattern of this group tended to be intensive, much of the work being done on single days which were spaced out. Only 14% of these active users completed some of the assignments, and no learners completed all the assignments required to complete the course. The pattern of assignment completion was similar to the first edition, with more assignments being completed for modules 1-3.

One learner completed the final Digital Fabrication task correctly, producing a good design for the Play House, but unfortunately didn’t complete all the other assignments.

There were registered learners from 64 countries from all continents. The main groups of learners by nationality were: USA 29%, India 5%, UK 5%, Brazil 5%, Canada 3%. From other countries there were generally 1-3 learners.

5.2.2 Discussion forums and feedback

The discussion forums for the modules were little used, some with zero contributions and the other with questions mainly topic focussed. Only one learner attempted to engage with other learners. Only one email direct to a tutor was received, with a question about process. Seven learners responded to the Canvas module survey, but not all completed all the questions. The responses were mainly positive about the course materials but provided little other information.

6 DISCUSSION

6.1 Original Evaluation plan

Following research into the use of MOOCs (Matkin, 2014) the evaluation was designed to focus on two main areas:

- a) how effective the MOOC has been as an environment to support learning
- b) the use of MOOC resources and methodologies within partner institutions

The data sources expected were:

a) Data obtained from the information recorded on registration and through the progress of individuals through the MOOC tasks.

The main data set collected include:

- Demographics of participants (gender, age, location / nationality, previous educational experience, possibly employment status)
- Reason for following MOOC
- Use of resources
- Completion of tasks / activities

b) Tutors participated in a focus group which sought information about their use of resources and the methods developed for the MOOC within their institutional context, including usage by their colleagues.

Summary of findings

a) This aspect of the evaluation was frustrated by the lack of information about learners and their activities. This was mainly because none of the learners provided the demographic or associated information requested. The use of resources and completion of tasks has been discussed in section 5.

b) Tutors indicated that they have brought together a mixture of resources for use in the MOOC. Some were pre-existing, some they created from new or from modifying existing resources, and some were collated from other sources. Most tutors subsequently used the resources in both their face-to-face teaching and within the MOOC. The introductory nature of the course meant that the resources were largely used by them in a similar context, but could also be available to colleagues who were co-tutors or teaching similar courses. Some of the resources originally produced for the MOOC have been so well received by the learners that they have been re-used and updated on an ongoing basis. Hence the MOOC activity has been proven to have made an important and useful contribution beyond its period of delivery.

6.2 Numbers registering

Despite the changes made to the delivery process the number of registered users for MOOC 2 was around 50% of that for the first edition of the MOOC. The largest change in recruitment was significantly less learners from the USA, with the global distribution of learners from other countries and continents being similar. There is no obvious reason for the difference in recruitment but the most likely reason is timing. The second edition was delivered during May – June. This may have overlapped

with the assignment submission and would almost certainly have overlapped with the end of semester examination periods for students in North America, Europe and some other countries. delivery period for MOOC 1 (September – November) would not have had the same overlaps.

The other significant change was no requirement for peer-learning. The first implementation was designed around tutor-supported peer-learning. The second was based on more activity-based learning, with peer-discussion left as an encouraged, but self-selected option. Given the engagement of learners in peer activities in the first implementation, this is unlikely to have had a significant effect on registration numbers.

6.3 Numbers completing

Relatively high sign-up and number of dropouts along with a small number of completers is common for MOOCs (Stacey, 2013). However, the number of individuals completing a significant number of assignments was smaller than expected. In the main those completing assignments did so within the targeted period of 4 hours/week study, but this data is predominantly for modules 1-3, from students who completed assignments.

Other factors which may have affected the numbers completing are based on limited data, but include:

- *Time input of tutors.* The first edition had more timetabled tutor input than the second one. Even though learners in the first edition did not appear to take advantage of this the literature indicates that contact with tutors is still a significant factor in fostering learner engagement (Stacey, 2013). There is insufficient data to be able to compare the background engagement of learners between the two editions.

- *Speed of response of tutors.* Tutors who responded to questions promptly established more of a dialogue with students than those who were slower.

- *Certificate of completion / Electronic badge.* The award for completion of the course was a single certificate or badge on completion of all modules. Some other MOOCs offer badges for completion of each module, so the realisation that this wasn't the case for this course may have affected learner motivation, engagement and completion.

6.4 Technical knowledge and ability requirements.

Although the course was designed to be suitable for students with no knowledge of Housing Design, the level of computational ability and requirement to build skills in using software for modules 3 and 4 may have been too demanding. The sharp drop-off in the number of active participants from modules 3 to 4 supports this, but it may have had an impact earlier, after the course started and learners began to engage with the materials more seriously. To try and counter this, in the second edition a non-parametric design option was included, but there was no significant change in the number of learners completing any of the modules.

7 CONCLUSIONS

Based on an appropriate combination of pedagogical models, a well-structured MOOC on the topic of housing design has been designed, implemented and delivered. To our knowledge, this was the first MOOC released on this topic and it is difficult to know the level of interest / size of student cohort which could be expected. Anecdotal comments from Canvas staff have indicated that the enrolment numbers for such a niche course were acceptable. Overall, the two iterations of the MOOC have provided access to resources to a large number of individuals, although completion rates on the courses were disappointing.

It is well known that only a small percentage of registered learners complete MOOCs, using them as opportunities for consumption of material. Other studies have also found limited engagement with discussion activity, for example the AI MOOC run by Edinburgh University identified only 4% of learners engaged in MOOC based discussion activities (MOOCs @ Edinburgh 2013).

The challenge going forward is to increase student engagement and completion rates for the course and we have identified a number of questions for further consideration:

- Who is our target audience? Should we choose a MOOC provider whose learners demographic is more European?
- With so many learners from the USA, was there a bias in the design of our learning materials which might affect learner engagement?
- Was the learning time and /or demands of the assessments too great?
- Should we leave out or re-instate the social-constructivist aspects of the modules?
- What would be the best time of year to run the programme, practically and to better integrate with OIKONET partners' programmes?

We have established that more learners actively participated in modules 1-3 than with the more demanding materials for module 4, the outputs of which were required for module 5. As a result, we are considering restructuring the course into two parts:

- Modules 1-3 are brought together into a stand-alone course, with the final output being a design which doesn't require parametric design software
- A separate course on Parametric Design and Digital Fabrication, made up of modules 4 and 5. Completion of modules 1-3 would be a pre-requisite for joining this course

Other changes will include:

- Electronic badges will be available on completion of each module
- Either the download requirements of the software required for module 4 will be reduced OR another option for completion of a design will be provided. Inclusion of both options would also be a possibility
- As part of the initial agreement, clearer definition of the data on student use and the format in which will be provided, from the environment provider.

Overall, the tutors have found the design, implementation and delivery of the MOOC and interesting and valuable activity, but one which raises important questions.

- What is the purpose of a MOOC, any MOOC?
- What defines the success of a MOOC, when so many of the learners are there for consumption of freely available material?

Leaving aside their potential as an advertising platform for the host institution(s), the purpose is an

important question for any tutors who wish to assess the success of their MOOC. For us it has been reassuring that active learners were able to work systematically through the materials provided. The biggest disappointment has been our inability to engage learners in peer learning activity, in the development of networks which support the social construction of their knowledge. Resolving this challenge will be a focus for future iterations of the OIKONET MOOC.

8 REFERENCES

Biggs, J. & Tang, C, (2011) *Teaching for Quality Learning at University*, SRHE & Open University Press, McGraw-Hill Education, Maidenhead. 4th Edition.

Bloom, B. S (Ed.) (1956). *Taxonomy of Educational Objectives, the classification of educational goals – Handbook I: Cognitive Domain*, McKay, New York.

Canvas (2014), *CANVAS network, about us*. Available at:
<https://www.canvas.net/pages/about-us>. (Accessed on March 15, 2015).

Matkin, G., W. (2014). *MOOC Research: What can we Learn and How?* Proceedings of the 7th International Conference of Education, Research and Innovation, Seville - 17-19 November 2014.

Riddy, P., Depuydt, J., & Madrazo, L. (2014) Designing for Learning. In Madrazo, L., Verbeke, J., Ooms, T., Riddy, P. (eds), *OIKODOMOS: Innovating Housing Learning* (pp. 32-47). Gent, Sint Lucas School of Architecture.

Stacey, P. (2013). *The Pedagogy of MOOCs*. Retrieved from
<https://edtechfrontier.com/2013/05/11/the-pedagogy-of-moocs/>

Van House, N. A. (2003). Digital Libraries and Collaborative Knowledge Construction, in A. P. Bishop, N. A. Van House, and B. P. Battenfield (eds), *Digital Library Use*, The MIT Press, Cambridge and London, pp. 271-295.

Vygotsky, L.S. (1978). *Mind and society: The development of higher mental processes*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press

9 APPENDIX A. DESIGN TEMPLATE

1) Theme / Title

Housing Design: From Concept to Fabrication:

Objective: to devise and implement a custom design process for housing integrating user's specific needs with environmental constraints through the use of advanced design and fabrication tools. Five complementary dimensions are addressed: participation, energy efficiency, sustainable materials, parametric design and digital fabrication.

2) Course Level (s)

(e.g. 1st year students, Master Students, preferably for students of the upper courses; ideally Master students.)

3) Pre-requisites

4) Coordinator (s)

Paul Riddy

5) Institution (s)

- University of Cyprus (Participatory processes, parametric design)
- Lisbon University Institute (Energy efficiency, Digital fabrication)
- Faculty of Architecture, Slovak University of Technology (Sustainable materials)

Other potential participants:

- School of Architecture of Valencia
- Department of Architecture (AF Belgrade)

6) Team and topic (s)

- Nadia Charalambous, University of Cyprus (Participatory processes)
- Elina Pattichi University of Cyprus (Parametric design)
- Vasco Moreira Rato, Lisbon University Institute (Energy efficiency, Digital fabrication)
- Alexandra Paio, Lisbon University Institute (Digital fabrication)
- Henrich Pifko, Faculty of Architecture, Slovak University of Technology (Sustainable materials)

7) Will there be any credits / awards (badges) associated with this MOOC

To be decided

8) Overall Sequence of Tasks during MOOC

- define the tasks in the topic descriptions below
- edit the topic name and task list within the table as appropriate
- include a brief description for each week when your task will run
- (within your topic description indicate the pre-requisite (PRs) tasks for each task)

[Will any of your tasks need to carry on beyond your topic week? What will you do in Week 6, include extra task if necessary]

	Week 1 Participatory Processes	Week 2 Energy Efficiency	Week 3 Sustainable Materials	Week 4 Parametric Design	Week 5 Digital Fabrication	Week 6 Round-Up
General Information / Activity	<i>Intro Learning Map</i>					<i>Competition voting</i>
TK1	Introduction-live talk	Video introductory lecture	Introduction – video lecture	Introduction Video lecture	Introduction video lecture	
TK2	Types of participatory processes – sample projects – best practices	Reading	Introduction – best-practice examples	Exercises with video tutorials (2): Advanced design software techniques for the integration of sustainability criteria into housing design.	Videos of 3 small practical exercises	
TK3	Reading and assignments –both theoretical texts and empirical studies	Live Forum	Sustainable materials – video lecture	Assignment with task support material and the use of advanced design software techniques. (Rhinoceros & Grasshopper) (1)	2 small assignments designing and milling	
TK4	Questionnaire design (individual and focus groups)		Sustainable materials – reading	Discussion forum-live	Discussion forum	

TK5	Live discussion- feedback		SM in design – real time peer activities			
TK6			SM in design – consultation			
TK7			Evaluation, inspiration – live discussion			

10 APPENDIX B. TOPIC DESCRIPTIONS

10.1 Module 1: Participatory Processes

Tutor: Nadia Charalambous, UCY

1) Overview of the topic including link(s) with MOOC Theme

An important part of the design process is involving the community in developing the environment and buildings in which they are going to live and/or share. The topic explores the underlying principle of the activity of community participation, that the environment works better if citizens are active and involved in its creation and management instead of being treated as passive consumers. Although public participation can be approached and defined in many different ways, this topic is concerned with participation aimed at issues involving community decision-making through the direct involvement of the public in the definition of their physical environment. The basic theoretical approaches are discussed, aiming at a basic understanding of the participatory process philosophy and principles. Familiarity with participatory approaches, methods and tools is also promoted through the presentation and discussion of key projects and practices.

2) Aims

Students will gain an understanding of the underlying principles and methods of community participation activities.

3) Learning Outcomes /goals

At the end of this MOOC topic the student should be able to:

LO1	<i>Describe basic approaches to participatory processes</i>
LO2	<i>Identify appropriate methods and tools applied to specific projects and practices</i>
LO3	<i>Design a questionnaire to obtain information from residents about their habitual life style</i>

4) For each Learning Outcome list the tasks/methods and the proposed resources

Learning Outcome	Task name/ Methods (e.g. live talk, video talk, peer activities - real time or asynchronous, tasks)	Resources (e.g. Case Repository, Oikopedia, Video 'lectures', social media, readings / network link, glossary, task support material etc.)
LO1	TK1 Live talk	Video lecture
LO2	TK2 Sample projects-best practices TK3 Reading and assignments	Readings/task support material
LO3	TK4 questionnaire design workshop TK5 Live discussion-feedback	Examples of previous questionnaires

5) Task Titles and descriptions

	Task Title	Task Description
TK1	Live talk	Video introduction with ppt (text, images, video). Basic approaches to participatory processes, key theoretical texts and framework, week's basic reading
TK2	Sample projects-best practices	Video presentation through ppt of important projects and best practices – description, analysis and criticism. Discussion on methodologies and tools used.
TK3	Reading assignments and	Choice of two key texts and one project to discuss and analyse
TK4	Questionnaire design workshop and assignment	Presentation and discussion of sample questionnaires in different cases. Design of questionnaire.
TK5	Live discussion-feedback	Live forum discussion

6) Will there be any (formative) Assessment associated with this topic? If so, what? (e.g. online quiz, peer review activity)

Online quiz and peer review activity

7) What are your expectations regarding the impact / influence of using MOOC?

- **For you as a teacher?**
The possibility to present and discuss the importance and potentials of participatory processes in contemporary design projects with students from different environments.
- **For your students?**
Students will gain both a broad understanding of the basic principles of community

participation and the basic skills required for its implementation through online resources.

- **For your course?**
Additional online resources and participation of students from around the world with different backgrounds and learning cultures.
- **For your institution?**
To include online learning resources

8) Background information required

Basic knowledge of the design process.

10.2 Module 2: Energy Efficiency

Tutor: Vasco Moreira Rato, ISCTE

1) Overview of the topic including link(s) with MOOC Theme.

This topic will address architectural design strategies to reduce energy consumption in residential buildings. These strategies will be framed in different climates and related to the levels of comfort and the patterns of use of the inhabitants.

This will be achieved through a video lecture, analysis of international case studies and a live discussion forum.

2) Aims

Integrate architectural design and climate to improve energy efficiency in residential buildings.

3) Learning Outcomes /goals

At the end of this MOOC topic the student should be able to:

LO1	Explain the relationship between architectural design and energy use in residential buildings.
LO2	Identify architectural design strategies for energy efficiency.
LO3	Describe how to implement design strategies in different climates.

4) For each Learning Outcome list the tasks/methods and the proposed resources

Learning Outcome	Task name/ Methods (e.g. live talk, video talk, peer activities - real time or asynchronous, tasks)	Resources (e.g. Case Repository, Oikopedia, Video 'lectures', social media, readings / network link, glossary, task support materiality, etc.)
LO1	Video introductory lecture	Video
LO2	Readings	Readings / Case repository from IEA (free access)
LO1+LO2+LO3	Discussion forum – live	-

5) Task Titles and descriptions

	Task Title	Task Description
TK1	Video introductory lecture	<p>Video introduction with slides and illustrations (20mn)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Welcome - Summary of the sub-topic and the work for the week - Basics about energy efficiency in residential buildings <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Why? - Energy use in the life cycle - Energy uses in the use phase - How to reduce energy consumption? - NZEBs - What depends on the architect? - Increased importance of embedded energy and carbon - What's next in this week's assignments?

TK2		Reading of (120mn): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - IEA SHC Task 40 report: “Solution Sets and Net Zero Energy Buildings - A review of 30 Net ZEBs case studies” pp. 85-130 (residential buildings) - IEA SHC Task 41 case studies site (only residential buildings): http://task41.iea-shc.org/casestudies/
TK3		Live forum discussion addressing the following topics (60mn) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How are passive strategies implemented? - How is architectural design influenced by different climates? - How is solar energy integrated within architecture?

6) Will there be any (formative) Assessment associated with this topic? If so, what? (e.g. online quiz, peer review activity)

Yes, provisionally. Participants are asked to make a short post (max 300 words) about one of the topics discussed in the discussion forums within a blog. Students then comment or respond on other’s posts, either paired or grouped in advance or within an open topic blog.

7) What are your expectations regarding the impact / influence of using MOOC?

- **For you as a teacher?**
The possibility of discussing energy efficiency from a broader perspective with participants from very different geographies;
To test a completely different approach to teaching, where there are no direct contact hours.
- **For your students?**
To have access to new learning resources that can be explored in an informal way.
- **For your course?**
To create a new module complementary to actual contact hours that will allow students to deepen their learning.
- **For your institution?**
To test the feasibility and impact of online learning resources.

8) Back ground information required

Basic knowledge of architectural design composition and construction systems.

10.3 Module 3: Sustainable Materials

Tutor: Henrich Pifko, FASTU

1) Overview of the topic including link(s) with MOOC Theme

Sustainable housing with its environmental, social and economic dimensions is affected by the life-cycle management of buildings. With increasing energy-efficiency the influence of used building materials starts to be crucial and architects have to consider this in their designs. On-line lectures will introduce the basics of this topic as well as interesting case studies, live discussions will teach the evaluation methods.

2) Aims

Integrate architectural design and sustainable use of building materials to improve LCA values in housing.

3) Learning Outcomes /goals

At the end of this MOOC topic the student should be able to:

LO1	...discuss the life-cycle of housing and the importance of material selection
LO2	...select and apply appropriate environment-friendly building materials
LO3	...include LCA and material selection to integrated design process

4) For each Learning Outcome list the tasks/methods and the proposed resources

Learning Outcome	Task name/ Methods (e.g. live talk, video talk, peer activities - real time or asynchronous, tasks)	Resources (e.g. Case Repository, Oikopedia, Video 'lectures', social media, readings / network link, glossary, task support material etc.)
LO1	Introduction, basics Best-practice examples Study: sustainable materials overview Sustainable materials details	Live video lecture TK1 TK3 Case Repository TK2 Oikopedia, Task support materials TK4 Live video lecture TK7
LO2	Use of sustainable materials in design Evaluation, self-evaluation	House sketch TK5 Peer reviewing TK6 ...network link
LO3	Materials in design process Live discussion, feedback	Role-playing game TK8 ...network link Online discussion, Social media

5) Task Titles and descriptions

	Task Title	Task Description
TK1	Introduction to Sustainable Materials – video lecture TK1-TK3: Block 1 -online 90min	Live video introduction with slides and illustrations (20 min) - Welcome, summary of the topic - Basics about LCA (see also ST2) - Healthy indoor environment - Sustainable building materials – properties, types... - Role of architect Discussion, Q&A, What's next?
TK2	Best-practice examples	Study of Case Repository (20 min) - Best practice examples of use of sustainable materials (pages will be created in March) On-line quiz, discussion, comments, summary (20min)
TK3	Sustainable materials – video lecture	Live video lecture (20min) - Environment-friendly materials, low-LCC materials - Material's influence on indoor environment - Low-tech and high-tech materials - Typical "green" materials: wood, earth, straw...

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Thermal insulations, interior surfaces... - Start and end of lifecycle, LCA methods, evaluation On-line quiz: checklist, evaluation of building, Q&A (10+ min)
TK4	Sustainable materials – reading TK4-TK5: Block 2: offline 90 min	Reading of relevant topics (75 min) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - On Oikopedia, Wikipedia, Task support materials - In additional supportive publications (to be selected yet)
TK5	Use of SM in design	Sketching a design using sustainable materials (15min)
TK6	Materials in design – reviewing Block 3 -online 90 min	Introduction, instructions (20 min) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Peer reviewing homework results in small groups (ca 4) - On-line quiz: checklist for self-evaluation
TK7	Constructions using sustainable materials	Live video lecture (20 min) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Details on use of selected materials - Summary
TK8	Evaluation, inspiration – live discussion Alt. without RPG to cut block 3 to 60 min	Live: How and why use SM? (20 min) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Group work – RPG architect-client... small groups (ca 4) - Discussion of inspirations / obstacles (from RPG) On-line quiz to evaluate achieved knowledge... (10 min) Summary, discussion, Q&A , end of task (20 min)

Total 4.5 hours: 90min online, 90min offline (individual study), 90min online

6) Will there be any (formative) Assessment associated with this topic? If so, what? (e.g. online quiz, peer review activity)

Peer review activity in TK6, on-line quiz at the end of TK7...

7) What are your expectations regarding the impact / influence of using MOOC?

- **For you as a teacher?**
Testing an innovative approach to teaching.
- **For your students?**
Access to learning resources that can be explored in less formal way.
- **For your course?**
Creation of a new module which enables participation of “external” students.
Preparation of additional study materials.
- **For your institution?**
Testing of the usability of architecture-specific online learning resources.

8) Back ground information required

Basic knowledge of architectural design composition and construction systems.

10.4 Module 4: Parametric Design

Tutor: Elina Pattichi, UCY

1) Overview of the topic including link(s) with MOOC Theme

The integration of different performance aspects in building design increases complexity of data and interdisciplinarity, rendering computational support necessary. Hence, massive amounts of data can be processed into comprehensible information with parametric techniques.

Aim of this topic, is the theoretical and practical investigation of parametric design strategies, for the integration of sustainability criteria into housing design. Parametric evaluation techniques are based on advanced digital generative processes that facilitate data flow for the design of environmentally efficient designs.

The main objective will be achieved with introduction in theory and practice with a video lecture, exercises on software techniques with video tutorials on a generic housing case study, task support material for the assignment of applying these techniques on each individual student case study and live discussion forum.

2) Aims

Students will investigate, understand and utilize the integration of sustainability criteria² into the geometry of their doll house case study with the use of a parametric process for the configuration of data-driven architectural design.

3) Learning Outcomes /goals

At the end of this MOOC topic the student should be able to:

LO1	Describe the application of parametric strategies (CAD) in housing design according to sustainability criteria.
LO2	Identify parametric strategies to correlate sustainability criteria with geometry in housing design.
LO3	Utilize the LO2 parametric processes in housing design according to the parameters of certain climate.

4) For each Learning Outcome list the tasks/methods and the proposed resources

Learning Outcome	Task name/ Methods (e.g. live talk, video talk, peer activities - real time or asynchronous, tasks)	Resources (e.g. Case Repository, Oikopedia, Video 'lectures', social media, readings / network link, glossary, task support material etc.)
LO1	Introduction	Video lecture
LO2	Exercises	Video tutorials
LO3	Assignment	Task support material
LO4	Discussion forum-live	

5) Task Titles and descriptions

	Task Title	Task Description
TK1	Introduction Video lecture	<p>Introduction with slides and illustrations (20 minutes):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Parametric Design and Generative Modelling • Parametric design and sustainable design • How to make a parametric diagram for the correlation of sustainability criteria with geometry • Examples of energy oriented parametric design case studies. • Examples of energy oriented parametric design in Grasshopper(Visual programming language/Rhinoceros).
TK2	Exercises with video tutorials (2): Advanced design software techniques for the integration of sustainability criteria into housing design.	<p>Tutorial 01: 20 minutes Task support material: Insolation chart (investigate winter solstice, summer solstice and equinox), Rhinoceros 2d model of the section of a South facing window and its parametric system in Grasshopper</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presentation of case study and performance evaluated with Parametric process in Grasshopper <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Explain geometry 2. Explain Insolation chart • Analysis of Grasshopper definition: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Introduction to Parametric design in Grasshopper 2. Building a Grasshopper Definition 3. Relating geometry in Rhino with Grasshopper definition 4. Variability in Grasshopper with a slider 5. Variability in Grasshopper according to the insolation char 6. Final output & discussion <p>Tutorial 02: 30 minutes Task support material: Insolation chart, Rhinoceros 3d model of a South facing planar facade and its parametric system in Grasshopper</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presentation of case study and performance evaluated with Parametric process in Grasshopper <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Explain geometry 2. Explain Insolation chart • Analysis of Grasshopper definition: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Introduction to Parametric design in Grasshopper 2. Relating 3d geometry in Rhino with Grasshopper definition 3. Variability in Grasshopper according to the insolation chart 4. Final output & discussion
TK3	Assignment with task support material and the use of advanced design software techniques. (Rhinoceros & Grasshopper) (1)	<p>Assignment (120 minutes): Implementation of parametric model on a planar facade according to students' housing proposal. The guidelines of this assignment include TK2 exercises and task support material. Students will use Rhinoceros software to design the planar facade. To optimize the facade's openings size and shading devises they will use a Grasshopper parametric system of tutorial 02 (TK2). Task support material: Insolation chart, Rhinoceros 3d model as a guidance for the students facade (floor and ceiling with three solid walls and the forth slot of wall open to design their proposal), Grasshopper parametric model (tutorial 02,TK2).</p>
TK4	Discussion forum-live	Discussion forum-live

6) Will there be any (formative) Assessment associated with this topic? If so, what?

Evaluation of the parametric and design output of the assignment.

7) What are your expectations regarding the impact / influence of using MOOC?

- **For you as a teacher?**
The innovative incorporation of theoretical and technical knowledge of digital parametric strategies in architectural design by a diverse group of learners.
- **For your students?**
Students will gain knowledge for the customised utilization of parametric processes in their designs and relate geometry with sustainability criteria according to parametric optimization techniques.
- **For your course?**
Application of parametric optimization strategies in the design of housing units under the use of advanced computer aided design techniques.
- **For your institution?**
Besides the development of new design methodology with digital strategies, the customised parametric techniques can be applied and adapted to various design problems.
(Under the housing course of UCY of professor Nadia Charalambous, it is proposed that the parametric strategies can be enhanced with space organization criteria.)

8) Back ground information required

CAD software

10.5 Module 5: Digital Fabrication

Tutor: Alexandra Paio (ISCTE)

1) Overview of the topic including link(s) with MOOC Theme.

This topic will address architectural design strategies based on an integrated theoretical and practical vision about digital fabrication (CAD/CAM) methods and techniques. The strategies presented will be rooted in the use of advance computational tools and digital fabrication equipment to optimize the output of housing design and construction. The main objective will be achieved through a video lecture introduction, small practical exercises videos, task support material and live discussion forum.

2) Aims

Students will gain critical skills needed to decide on the most relevant technologies to digitally fabricate architectural design solutions.

3) Learning Outcomes /goals

At the end of this MOOC topic the student should be able to:

LO1	Describe various methods and techniques of digital fabrication (CAD / CAM)
LO2	Identify and explain methodologies to approach digital processes applied to specific architectural design strategies solutions
LO3	Complete small design and fabrication tasks which integrate the use of technology

4) For each Learning Outcome list the tasks/methods and the proposed resources

Learning Outcome	Task name/ Methods (e.g. live talk, video talk, peer activities - real time or asynchronous, tasks)	Resources (e.g. Case Repository, Oikopedia, Video 'lectures', social media, readings / network link, glossary, task support materials etc.)
LO1	Introduction video lecture	Video
LO2	Small practical exercises videos	Video
LO3	Small assignments	Task support material
	Discussion forum - live	

5) Task Titles and descriptions

	Task Title	Task Description
TK1	Introduction video lecture	Video introduction with slides and images (20 minutes) Fundamentals of digital processes (CAD / CAM): - Origins and concepts of digital processes; - Digital processes - addition (SLS, SLA, LOM, FDM, 3DP ...); subtraction (laser cutting, water jet cutting, milling); formative (folding, stamping, moulding ...); assembly (robotic); - paradigmatic examples applied to specific architectural design strategies solutions;

		What's next week's videos
TK2	3 small practical exercises videos	Video introduction with slides and images (10 minutes each) Application of CAD / CAM technologies: - Planning the design for manufacturing (laser cutting, CNC Milling, 3D print); - Handling of digital manufacturing technologies. What's next week's assignments
TK3	2 small assignments	Application of specific CAD / CAM technologies to (60 minutes each) - CNC Milling practical assignment; - 3D print practical assignment.
TK4	Discussion forum	Live forum discussion

6) Will there be any (formative) Assessment associated with this topic? If so, what?

On line quiz

7) What are your expectations regarding the impact / influence of using MOOC?

- **For you as a teacher?**
The possibility of discussing architectural design strategies based on an integrated theoretical and practical vision about digital fabrication (CAD/CAM) methods and techniques with students from around the world.
- **For your students?**
Students will gain critical skills needed to decide on the most relevant technologies to digitally fabricate for architecture and construction through additive, subtractive (2D and 3D) processes.
- **For your course?**
Use of advance computational tools and digital fabrication equipment will optimize the output of housing design and construction.
- **For your institution?**
The adopted methods will support the development of new design strategies applied to housing design and construction.

8) Background information required

Basic knowledge of CAD technologies

10.6 Tutors biographies

Nadia Charalambous trained as an architect and has been working as an academic and researcher at the University of Cyprus since 2008. She studied Architecture at the Bartlett School of Architecture, University College London, University of London where she received her BSc. in Architecture and Environmental Studies, M.Sc. in Advanced Architectural Studies and the Diploma in Architecture. She subsequently completed her Ph.D. studies at the National Technical University in Athens, NTUA. Underpinning all research and professional activities is a continuous interest in the complex relationship between spatial configuration and social phenomena, both in the education and in the practice of architecture. The complex relationship of spatiality and sociability is approached from a variety of analytical perspectives, including both quantitative as well as qualitative research tools. Past and planned research activities acknowledge the need for an interdisciplinary approach to take account of both the spatial, social and other aspects of the built environment and focus on the relationship between urban form, segregation and conflict both in residential and public space in the city.

Vasco Moreira Rato is assistant professor at the Dpt. of Architecture and Urbanism, ISCTE-University Institute of Lisbon, where he coordinates the scientific area of architecture technology. He holds a degree in Architecture, a MSc. in Construction and a PhD. in Civil Engineering (Rehabilitation of the Built Heritage). He has academic and corporate professional experience in materials for architecture and buildings renovation, project management in architectural conservation, construction technology and energy efficiency in buildings. Currently, he develops teaching and research activities related to sustainability, energy efficiency, materials, ecology and technology in architecture.

Heinrich Pifko is architect, assistant professor at the Faculty of Architecture of the Slovak University of Technology in Bratislava (institute for Ecological and Experimental Design). His field in research, in education and in design practice is sustainable and energy-efficient architecture. He was leading author rep. editor of books *Efficient Housing (Efektívne bývanie, Eurostav 2008)* and *Manual of Sustainable Architecture (Rukoväť udržateľnej architektúry, SKA 2013)*. He is chairman of the Passive House Institute in Slovakia and founding member of ArTUR organisation, dealing first of all with natural building materials and indoor environment quality. He also leads “Architecture 2020” centre at the Faculty.

Elina Pattichi is currently collaborating with professor Nadia Charalambous in the OIKONET project representing the Department of Architecture of the University of Cyprus. She has taught at the University of Nicosia and worked as researcher at the University of Cyprus for the preparation of a research proposal under the agenda of energy efficient modular approach for deep renovation of buildings using novel adaptable skins and RES.

Elina holds a B-Arch with Honours from the National Technical University of Athens (2009) and March from the Architectural Association, Design Research Laboratory (2011). The research realized during Design Research Laboratory master under Proto-design agenda, included the investigation of robotic behaviour and analogue/digital computation of funicular shapes, parametric articulation of bifurcating l-system geometries and real time physical/digital recognition system for prefabricated inflatable components.

She is founder and director of the young and internationally awarded architectural firm EP Architects. She is also founder of ATRAKTOS design & innovation established in 2013 as an independent interdisciplinary collaborative with the initiative to combine different engineering disciplines for research based investigation of design methodology and manufacturing techniques using CAD-CAM technology.

Alexandra Paio is an Assistant Professor in the Department of Architecture and Urbanism at ISCTE-IUL. Director and Researcher of VitruviusFabLab-IUL and Researcher at ISTAR-IUL. Co-Director of Advanced Studies Course in Digital Architecture (ISCTE-IUL+FAUP). PhD in Architecture and Urbanism at ISCTE-IUL, entitled “urbanGENE: An Urban Grammar for Portuguese Settlements from the 16th to the 18th century”. Research at “OIKONET. A global multidisciplinary network on housing research and learning” (co-financed by European Union). Her main research interests are Computational Design, Digital tools and processes to support the creative design, Interactive architecture, Shape Grammars, and Digital Fabrication.

10.7 Section 3: Links to OIKONET Project Goals

1) Please tick (✓) the project goals to which the MOOC will contribute:

OIKONET Project Goals	tick
Promoting cooperation between research, education and society , by bringing together stakeholders from different areas to formulate and discuss contemporary problems regarding housing at a European and global scale.	✓
Providing students, teachers, researchers and other stakeholders with the competences necessary to work in a readily accessible international environment	✓
Encouraging the active participation of these stakeholders in the creation of innovative learning spaces which overcome disciplinary and institutional boundaries	✓
Facilitating cooperation between different academic programs which include housing (in its different dimensions) as subject matter.	✓
Fostering physical and virtual mobility across partner institutions, by means of workshops, seminars, conferences and shared learning activities in blended learning scenarios dedicated to study contemporary housing issues.	✓
Contributing to the internationalisation of the European cooperation , incorporating third countries to the network. This will facilitate the exchange and mobility at the international level, preparing the ground for further cooperation among network partners in future programs (Erasmus Mundus).	?
Promoting new forms of international cooperation , through the design and implementation of shared learning activities carried out following a blended learning approach with the digital environments of the OIKODOMOS virtual campus.	✓
Establishing evaluation procedures to guarantee the quality of the pedagogic activities to be implemented by network partners, in mixed formal and informal pedagogical settings.	✓
Reinforcing the societal roles of academic institutions in a culturally and linguistically diverse Europe, by embedding the learning activities in those social milieus in which solutions for housing problems are needed (integration, immigration) thus activating knowledge through interaction with society.	✓
Enhancing interdisciplinarity and transdisciplinarity , by creating new learning spaces which bring together different disciplines into the solution of housing problems.	✓
Contributing to the development of technology enhanced learning , embedding ICT in the learning processes and learning structures.	✓

11 GLOSSARY

Blooms Taxonomy

The main elements of this taxonomy of educational objectives for the Cognitive Domain are provided in Fig. 2 above. For each level of the taxonomy Bloom (Bloom, 1956) provided examples of verbs which could be used to describe the cognitive activity of a learner, for example list, describe, apply which would be appropriate for the first three levels. The verbs have been used extensively in the writing of learning outcomes, which in turn support the design of aligned learning, as described in constructive alignment. Bloom also elaborated taxonomies and lists of verbs for Affective and Psychomotor Domains.

Constructive Alignment

Refers to a model for the design of learning proposed by Biggs (Biggs et al, 2011) illustrated in Fig 1 above. Based around careful selection and alignment of all the main learning elements to support constructive development of a students' learning. The (aims and) learning outcomes are used to define the learning which learners will be able to demonstrate, allowing selection of the other elements as part of an iterative cycle of development. Blooms taxonomy are used to select the verbs which are used within the learning outcomes.

MOOC, Massive Open Online Course

The term is self-explanatory in that the words of the acronym reflect the design of the MOOC. Because they cater for very large numbers of students (hundreds to thousands) who are usually geographically dispersed, conventional approaches to online teaching are supplemented with activities which promote learning from peers.